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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

PREMARITAL TESTS AMONG THE MUSLIM IN NIGERIA: AN ASSESSMENT OF NASARAWA STATE MUSLIMS UMMAH

Aliyu Ibrahim Musaddad

Department of Islamic Studies, Faculty of Arts,
Nasarawa state university keffi,
Nasarawa state,
Nigeria.

Email: aliyumusaddad@gmail.com

Aliyu Umar PhD

Department of Islamic Studies, Faculty of Arts,
Nasarawa state university keffi,
Nasarawa state,
Nigeria.

Email: dandamau@gmail.com

Khadija Ishaq

Department of Islamic Studies, Faculty of Arts,
Nasarawa state university keffi,
Nasarawa state,
Nigeria.

Email: khadijaishaq33@gmail.com

Abstract

The advancement in science and technology has led to the detection of diseases affecting humans, and those which could give room to more diseases if it is not matched with a couple that is not suitable. The level of marriage conducted in Nasarawa State without pre-marital test is becoming alarming. Most couples in Nasarawa State felt disturbed on the issue of pre-marital tests for the fear of a result that could deteriorate their plan of marriage. Hence, most people give preferences to go to a wedding without a pre-marital test. This study assessed pre-marital tests among Muslim couples of Nasarawa State. Being a field survey, the study collected data from both primary and secondary sources. A total of 100 respondents 33 from each of the three senatorial zones were selected through random sampling. A questionnaire was used as the main instrument for data collection. The data collected were analysed using a simple percentage technique. The findings of the study found out that the level of awareness about the significance of pre-marital screening for couples is increasing

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with few numbers of people disdaining it because of the fear of an unfavourable result that might hinder the planning of their wedding. Based on the findings, it is recommended that an intensive enlightenment campaign onpre-marital testing before marriage should be done by the government and institutions through the media, alongside health education on genetic disease and its prevention right from the primary school level.

Keywords: Premarital, Tests, Muslim, Nigeria, Nasarawa State, Muslims, *Ummah*.

INTRODUCTION

The advancement in science and technology has led to the detection of diseases affecting humans which could give room to more diseases if it is not matched with a couple that is not suitable (Qasim 2). Despite the widespread of many diseases, advancements in genetic engineering have led to considerable improvements in diagnosing these diseases. Therefore, pressure on prospective spouses to undergo premarital medical exams has increased significantly in contemporary society (Qasim 2).

Many Muslims have responded to this emerging need by making some premarital screening tests compulsory for a marriage. The adoption of these policies comes from the core message of Islam, which encourages counselling to protect future generations and to guarantee the continuity of worshipping God. However, some people reject the compulsory test, considering them unnecessary according to their beliefs and custom (Ibrahim 4).

A premarital test is defined as a test in which intending couples are tested for genetic, infectious and blood-transmitted diseases to prevent any risk of transmitting the disease to their partners or children. It provides the baseline assessment of prospective marriage couples to reduce the unproductive genetic risk and also reduces the incidence of babies born with common haemoglobinopathies and infectious diseases (Sharaf, 2).

Premarital screening consists of a comprehensive group of a test, especially for those who are planning to get married. According to World Health Organization, 5% of the world population carries genes responsible for haemoglobinopathies and that Sickle cell anaemia is particularly common among people whose ancestors comes from sub-Saharan Africa, India, and Saudi Arabia and Mediterranean countries (El-Hazimi 21).

In some places in Nigeria today, marriage arrangement is always accompanied by premarital test. This is done to reduce the rate of transferable infections. There have been campaigns on the significance of the premarital test. However, the level of the premarital test has not increased significantly. This is due to the negative pre-conception about the premarital test. Spouses are normally discouraged to go for such tests for fear of incompatibility that might hinder their marriage arrangement. Thus, it is against this background that this study intends to assess the level and attitudes of Muslims of Nasarawa State towards the premarital test.

The level of marriage conducted in Nasarawa state without premarital test is becoming alarming. Most couples in the state felt disturbed on the issue of

premarital tests for the fear of a result that could deteriorate their plan of marriage.

This study aims to assess premarital tests among Muslim couples in Nasarawa State and suggest a way of encouraging them. The objectives of the study are to determine the level of premarital tests among Muslim couples, to examine the attitude of Muslim couples toward the premarital test, to investigate the position of premarital test in Islam, Find out the effort of parents and scholars towards encouraging premarital test and to proffer solution to the problem associated with premarital test among Muslim couples in Nasarawa State.

This study has numerous significance among which it will create awareness on the significance of the premarital test, especially for the couple intending to marry. It will encourage parents and stakeholders to reshuffle their perception of premarital tests to reduce the prevalence of unwanted genetic order and diseases for the future of their children/ward. it will also stimulate government and policymakers to make a law for any couples intending to marry to have a certified premarital test to reduce the rate of communicable disease that might not only affect the couples but also put their children (offspring) in danger.

METHODOLOGY

The study employs both interview and Questioners methods of research it designs in investigating and assessing premarital tests in Nasarawa State among the Muslims *Ummah*. Being field research, the methodology adopted by the researcher involves both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources involve the researcher's observation, oral interview, Qur'an and Hadiths. Meanwhile, the secondary sources involve documented studies such as Textbooks, Journals, Pamphlet, Magazines, Conference papers and other materials on web pages.

The work focuses on Nasarawa State with a special emphasis on Muslims couples. The choice of this area will allow for thorough research. The research is a quantitative one, which adopts an interview and Questioner targeting a couple who got married and those about to get it. A simple is made on one local Government each from the three senatorial zones as thus; Lafia from southern zone, Akwanga from Northern zone and keffi from the Western zone.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Overview of Pre-Marital Test

Marriage under Islamic law can be defined as a lawful union between a male and female by the formal way prescribed under Islamic family law. It prevents Muslims spiritually, physically, emotionally and psychologically here on the earth, and it is a gateway to *al-Jannah* (Paradise) on the Day hereafter (Shahzad, 10). Generally, Muslims consider marriage as a form of *Ibadah* (worship) that provides companionship, sexual gratification and affection between spouses.

There are several reasons why the pre-marital test is encouraged among

couples which include:

- 1- *A premarital test is a test that offers a crucial health assessment of soon-to-be-married couples in which they are tested for genetic, infectious and transmissible diseases to prevent any risk of transmitting any disease to each other and their children.*
- 2- *Marriage is considered a remarkable event in a couple's life, as they plan to start a family, and through which they usher in a new stage in terms of building emotional, social, familial and healthy relationships, hence the need for the pre-marital test is obvious.*
- 3- *Gauge the positive health status of prospective bride and groom*
- 4- *Detect infectious diseases – Hepatitis B infection, HIV, HCV and other sexually transmitted diseases as well as sickle test etc.*
- 5- *Identify carriers of genetic disorders, to assess the risk of having children with a severe form of the disease. The couple can then choose whether or not to have an affected child. e.g.*

Thalassemia, Haemophilia and Sickle Cell Disease Tests that constitute Pre-marital Screening:

- 1) **Routine Investigations** – *Complete Blood Count (CBC), Complete Urine Analysis and Peripheral Blood Smears to check for normal and abnormal cells. Blood group testing (ABO-RH) is important to screen out the Rh-negative women and counsel them about the risks in pregnancy.*
- 2) **Infectious Diseases** - *VDRL for Syphilis Testing HIV – I and II Hepatitis-B Screening Hepatitis-C Virus*
- 3) **Genetic Tests** - *The doctor usually goes for culture-based genetic screening. Depending on your family history and ancestry different tests are designed for different disorders like thalassemia.*

The tests are specially referred to in 'consanguineous marriages' or relationships by blood or common ancestry, in which the chances of offspring inheriting a recessive allele for a disease are increased. The closer the relationship, the greater the risk.

Genetic tests are done by analyzing small samples of blood or body tissues.

The significance of the pre-marital test cannot be overemphasized. Being it one of the foundations for successful and healthy strategies in modern marriage.

Islamic Position on Pre-Marital Test

A pre-marital medical examination is a fundamental phenomenon for the sustainability of marriage between couples. It helps in securing their lives as well as shaping the fate and future of their prospective children. Pre-marital medical examination nowadays goes beyond the doctrine of *darurah* (necessity). It is a mechanism to be used to achieve the fundamental objective of Shari'ah (Islamic law), that is, safeguarding people's lives and morality. Islam values human life,

health and morality more than anything one can think of. Hence, Islam encourages Muslims to do anything that can prevent loss of human life or anything that can lead to protection and enhancement of people health and morality. To this end, the Almighty Allah said,

...whoever saves a single soul as if he saves the lives of the entire mankind (5:32).

Given this, prospective parents should as a matter of obedience to the law of Allah, examine their health status so that they cannot cheat themselves and as well, cheat the younger generations. To this effect, the Prophet (s.a.w) was reported to have said:

A patient will not come closer to a healthy one (Bukhari, 12:288).

Islam encourages prospective spouses to conduct a medical examination before their marriage contract, as it is significant to the health sustainability in the community. It is very important to conduct a pre-marital medical examination because the rate of incurable and communicable diseases is increasing rapidly in the community, most especially in developing countries. Such diseases include HIV, HBV, HCV and other infectious diseases that have to do with people's genotype.

Although, this concept of pre-marital medical examination is not among the essential elements required for a valid marriage in Islam. However, that does not prevent leaders from making it a mandatory rule upon the prospective spouses.

One of the features of Islamic law is dynamism, that is to say, Islam always goes with time. Thus, the following points are pertinent in determining the reasons for conducting medical examination before a marriage contract:

- i. ensuring the health status of the marrying couples, as Islam dislike being cheated and it does not allow harming one another;*
- ii. Sustainability of the Islamic objective of marriage (procreation). As it can only be achieved in a status of a good health condition;*
- iii. protection and control of moral decadence of the younger generation against the effect or repercussion of*
- iv. Unhealthy parents may likely not going to survive.*

The above points have been canvassed in line with the criteria set out by some of the Islamic scholars. Thus, according to Amidi, in making the derivation of any rule in Islamic jurisprudence, a statement of the basic issue and valid arguments for the correct or preferred position should be maintained (Bernard, 48).

This, of course, has been a case of discussion among scholars, where arguments have been canvassed on the effects of parental mortality against the future of younger generations. In the words of *Wael*, "Devices used to be considered in introducing new rules into Shari'ah inter alia include: the principle of "*Darurah*" (necessity); the principle of derivation; *Takhayyur* (selection) and *Talfiq* (amalgamation) approaches; an interpretive approach which sometimes

known as *neo-ijtihād*; and adoption of a principle which says any law that does not contradict the principle of Shari'ah may be deemed lawful (Hallak, 115).

Indeed, such proofs have been exhibited by scholars, to the effect that lack of pre-marital medical examination causes a high rate of parental mortality which will have a repercussion on the future of the younger generation.

It was against the above backdrop that in some of the Muslim and Muslims dominated countries such as Saudi Arabia, U.A.E, Bahrain, Egypt, Syria, Lebanon, Tunisia and Morocco, a pre-marital medical examination has been considered as an avenue for protecting people against the effect of genetic and congenital disorder, as it is common in such societies. Most of those countries began with encouragement to conduct an optional pre-marital medical examination, so that citizens may reflect on its significance in their marital life. When the problems of contagious diseases continue to escalate among their people, they did not relent in taking necessary action to counter the menace. Thus, for instance, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in 2004 has further stepped forward to make pre-marital medical examination compulsory on spouses. The implementation of such a Decree was first preceded by making the provision of complete health facilities affordable to the citizens by the government (Fahad, 29). This has reiterated the government commitments towards ensuring the successful implementation of its policies in line with the principles of Shari'ah in the country.

The essence of pre-marital medical examination in addition to the prevention of parental mortality is to also prevent prenatal transmission and inflectional diseases which mostly affect the fetus or unborn child. Even if the child has been luckily born, there is every tendency for him to be infected with his parents inherited disease in the future (Fahad, 29). Given this, one may conclude that the conduct of pre-marital medical examination is not all about the concept of *darurah* (necessity) but it is also a religious obligation.

Explicitly, Islam does not make the pre-marital medical examination mandatory on spouses, and at the same time, it does not prevent Muslims from checking their health status before delving into a marriage contract. Although, some muftis do not agree in *toto* with any attempt to make it mandatory upon spouses because none of the Qur'an or Sunnah declares it as such. To this end, when Shaykh Ibn Jibrin was asked about the issue of making a pre-marital examination a condition precedent for a marriage contract in Islam, he had this to say:

All perfect praise be to Allah, The Lord of the Worlds. I testify that there is none worthy of worship except Allah and that Muhammad (SAW) is His slave and Messenger. It is permissible, if Allah wills, to carry out a medical examination before marriage. This becomes even more confirmed if it is predominantly believed that there are hereditary diseases in the family (Ibn Jibrin, 3).

However, when he was asked further about its legal position in Shari'ah, then he said:

It is permissible to do so if an internal disease is feared which would affect one's health, prevent the comfort of the spouses and the stability and tranquillity of life. As it might be that one of them is possessed [by jinn] or has epilepsy, or he/she has a chronic disease even though the disease may be a simple one, like asthma, diabetes, bilharzia, or rheumatism. The same thing applies to being sterile and not being able to have children. However, if the spouses appear to be in good health and the environment and the society where they live has no such diseases or similar ones, then, in principle, they are not affected by any disease and one should not fear anything about them. In which case, there is no need for a medical examination for both spouses. Allah Knows best (Ibn Jibrin 5).

The first statement quoted above implies that nobody is allowed to impose something which Allah (S.W.T) did not make mandatory on people. Had he wished, he would have made it so, but out of His mercy, he overlooked it. To supplement this idea further, the Prophet (S.A.W) was reported to have said:

Verily Allah the Almighty has prescribed the obligatory deeds, so do not neglect them; He has set certain limits, so do not go beyond them; He has forbidden certain things, so do not indulge in them; and He has said nothing about certain things, as an act of mercy to you, not out of forgetfulness, so do not go enquiring into these (Nawawi, Hadith 40).

The second Quotation implies that, despite the implicit nature of a mandatory pre-marital medical examination under Shari'ah, still there is also no explicit provision in the Qur'an and Sunnah that prohibits decreeing pre-marital medical examination as mandatory. Therefore, it is not permissible for Muslims to forbid what Allah has not made forbidden, as he might have left it silent as an act of mercy upon the believers (Jamal, 30)

DATA PRESENTATION

Level of Pre-Marital Test among Muslim Couples in Nasarawa State

Despite the widespread of many diseases, advancements in genetic engineering have led to considerable improvements in diagnosing hereditary and sexually transmitted diseases. Therefore, pressure on prospective spouses to undergo pre-marital medical tests has increased significantly.

Jaji revealed in an oral interview that despite the relatively high level of knowledge about diseases, either those that can be transmitted from one of the couples to another such as HIV and STDs or those which will affect the hereditary composition of the children such as sickle cell anaemia, about one-third of the couple intending to marry in Nasarawa State were still reluctant to carry out pre-marital testing.

In an oral interview with MalamaKhadijat who is a medical practitioner in Lafia expressed that there is a significant increase in the level of pre-marital tests among Muslim couples in keffi. This is proved in the sense that before most marriages are conducted, the two parties involved always demand medical

certificates of fitness from the couples from approved health facilities.

In another interview with Malam Sani of UngwanMainaLafia revealed that the level of the pre-marital test is improving these days with the widespread of transmitting diseases such as HIV/AIDs and sickle cell anaemia.

Mal. Usman also stressed that there is a significant increase in the level of pre-marital tests among Muslim couples in Akwanga. This arose out of the fear of encouraging hereditary diseases and preventing the continuous spread of deadly diseases such as HIV and other sexually transmitted diseases.

AlhajiBabangida revealed in an interview that for fear of deadly diseases, most Muslims were today forced to embark on the pre-marital test. He lamented however that not all people always supported that, but the majority of the parents or stakeholders in charge of the marriage always seeks a verified medical certificate of fitness as evidence.

From the above disposition, there is an indication that most people in Nasarawa State have embraced pre-marital tests for the couple intending to marry and it is being on a steady increase as a result of the widespread of diseases.

Awareness of Pre-Marital Test among Muslims of Nasarawa State.

As a result of the widespread of contagious diseases, the need for pre-marital tests becomes obvious. Many stakeholders have responded to this emerging need by making pre-marital screening tests compulsory for a marriage. The adoption of these policies comes from the core message of Islam, which encourages counselling to protect future generations and to guarantee the continuity of worshipping God.

Dr Ilyas, a medical practitioner in DalhatuAraf has this to say concerning the knowledge of pre-marital testing among people of Lafia:

It is obvious that some people do not know about pre-marital health screening and even if they have heard it from the media. It is also discovered that some people attitude towards pre-marital health screening is relatively poor. Also, adequate attention is yet to be given to the need to educate society at large on human developments and in human genetics, their application in health and wellbeing in Lafia is relatively low. Hence, there is much left to be done.

He stressed further that:

Based on our records, the incidence of sickle cell, trait and sickle cell anaemia among infants in Lafia is relatively high which is due to the lack of knowledge about their partner's genotype and poor attitude towards pre-marital health screening during their courting.

Attitudes of Muslim towards Pre-Marital Test in Lafia

Majority of people intending to marry feel reluctant to undergo a pre-marital test for the fear of any result that might hinder their marriage plan. In line with the above, Jaji stressed that about 70% of people believed that the pre-

marital test is necessary and supported the view of making the pre-marital test compulsory, while about 30% of Muslims in Lafia on the contrary are not in support of the screening test. This unwillingness to perform the pre-marital test is associated with less educational background and family background.

Malam Kayyimu rightly pointed that the overall attitude of Muslims regarding the pre-marital test is sometimes been associated with the teaching of predestination. The emerging view is that the Pre-marital test has either been condemned or condoned in the Muslim society of Lafia. According to him, as a result of lack of knowledge and exposure, some people considered that pre-marital is not necessary. They also believed that Pre-marital test has no potential to limit the spread of diseases.

Abdullahi on the other hand stressed that the majority of Muslims in Lafia believed that the pre-marital test is important because of its potentiality to limit hereditary diseases.

Efforts of Parents and Scholars towards Encouraging Pre-Marital Test in Lafia.

Controversy abounds on making Pre-marital tests mandatory for all individuals who would decide to get married. While some scholars supported mandatory pre-marital tests, others were reluctant in supporting the view.

Perception of Muslim Couple of Nasarawa on Pre-Marital Test

Presents the information collected from respondents from interviews and questionnaires concerning pre-marital tests among Muslims of Lafia.

Data of the Respondents

1- Gender

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	42	42
Female	58	58
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th June 2021

The table above shows the sex distribution of the respondents contacted. 42% of the respondents are male, while 58% of the respondents are females. This indicates that females dominated the respondents.

2- Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-18	10	10
19-30	70	70
31 above	20	20
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th June 2021

The table above shows that 10% of the respondents are aged 1-18, while

70% are aged 19-30 while 20% are 31years above. This indicates that respondents between the age of 19-30 years dominated the study.

3- Educational Qualification

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
FSLC	8	8
SSCE	40	40
NCE/ND	32	32
B.Sc Degree/HND	18	18
Postgraduate	2	2
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th June 2021

The table above shows that 8% of the respondents hold First School Leaving Certificate, 40% hold Senior Secondary School Certificate, 32% hold NCE/National Diploma while,18% hold B.Sc Degree and 2% are holders of postgraduate certificates.

4- Islamic Knowledge

Level of Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Basic	56	56
Advanced	34	34
Very Advanced	10	10
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th June 2021

The table above shows that 56% of the respondents have basic Knowledge about Islam, while 34% have advanced knowledge about Islam and 10% have advanced knowledge about Islam.

Response to the Questions

Question 1: Do you know about the Pre-marital test?

Level of Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	70	70
No	30	30
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th June 2021

The table above shows that 70% of the respondent maintained that they know pre-marital tests, while 30% of the respondents stressed that they do not know the pre-marital test. By implication, the respondents maintained that they know the pre-marital test.

Question 2: Which of them do you know?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
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HIV/AID	44	44
STI/STDs	16	16
Hepatitis	16	16
All of the above	24	24
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th May 2021

The table above shows that 44% of the respondents know about the pre-marital test on HIV/AIDs, 18%, on the other hand, know about the pre-marital test for STI/STDs while 16% know about the pre-marital test on Hepatitis and 24% maintained that they know pre-marital test on all the aforementioned. By implication, the respondents maintained that they know pre-marital tests on HIV and AIDs.

Question 3: Do you do it before marriage or intend to do it?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	58	58
No	42	42
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th May 2021

From the table above, 58% of the respondents stressed that they had a Pre-marital test or intend to do it before their marriage, while 38% on the other hand maintained that they have not done a pre-marital test before their marriage. By implication, the respondents maintained that they had or will have a pre-marital test before their marriage.

Question 4: Do you support the idea of the pre-marital test?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	30	30
Agree	26	26
Indifference	20	20
Disagree	16	16
Strongly Disagree	8	8
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th May 2021

From the table above, 30% of the respondents strongly support the idea of the pre-marital test, while 26% support the idea. 20% on the other hand neither supported nor held the idea in contempt. Among the respondents, 16% disagreed with the idea of pre-marital test and 8% strongly disagreed. By implication, the respondents strongly support the idea of the pre-marital test.

Question 5: From your understanding of Islam, what is the position of *Sharia* on the Pre-marital test?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Unanimously	22	22
Recommended	40	40
Lawful	8	8
Hated	10	10
Unlawful	20	20
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 24th May 2021

The table above shows the position of the respondents on pre-marital tests based on their understanding of Islam. 22% among them are unanimous on the issue, while 40% recommended it and 8% considered it lawful. On the other hand, 10% hated the practice and 20% considered it unlawful. By implication, the respondents recommended the practice of pre-marital tests.

Question 6: Do you think it should be encouraged?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	64	64
No	36	36
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The table above shows that 64% of the respondents believed that pre-marital tests should be encouraged, while 36% do not support the encouragement of pre-marital tests. By implication, the respondents rightly support the encouragement of pre-marital tests.

Question 7: Are the people of Nasarawa State metropolis firmly engaged in pre-marital screening?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	40	40
No	60	60
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The tables above shows that 40% of the respondent stressed that people of Nasarawa State are firmly engaged in pre-marital screening, while 60% maintained that people of Nasarawa State are not firmly engaged in pre-marital screening. By implication, the respondents stressed that the people of Nasarawa State are not firmly engaged in pre-marital screening.

Question 8: Do you think doing it will strengthen the marital life of Muslim couples in Nasarawa State?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	72	72
No	28	28
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The table above shows that 72%% of the respondent believed that doing pre-marital screening will strengthen the marital life of Muslim couples in Nasarawa State, while 28% on the other believed that doing pre-marital screening will not strengthen the Marital life of Muslim couples in Nasarawa State. By implication, the respondents firmly believed that doing pre-marital screening will strengthen the marital life of Muslim couples in Nasarawa State.

Question 9: Do you know your status?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	42	42
No	58	58
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The table above shows that 42% of the respondent concurred that they knew their health status, while 58% on the other hand concurred that they do not know their health status. By implication, the respondents concurred that they do not know their health status.

Question 10: Do you know the status of your partner?

Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	46	46
No	54	54
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The table above shows that 46% of the respondent maintained that they knew their partner's health status, while 54% on the other hand maintained that they do not know the health status of their partner. By implication, the respondents stressed that they do not know the health status of their partners.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

From the questionnaire distributed on the issue of pre-marital screening among Muslims of Lafia, the following findings were revealed:

- i. *The majority of Muslims in Nasarawa State know pre-marital screening. Most of them stressed that they got that knowledge through publications, sensitization campaigns, media, friends and others.*
- ii. *The findings also revealed that Muslims of Nasarawa are most concerned about the pre-marital test for HIV and AIDs. Less consideration is given to others such as Sickle cells, STI/STDs and Hepatitis.*
- iii. *Due to the level of their knowledge about diseases such as HIV/AIDs and other STI/STDs, most of the Muslims in Nasarawa state engaged in pre-marital screening. Even those who have not married stressed that they will do it before their marriage. Hence, by so doing, it is proven that Muslims of*

Nasarawa State strongly support the idea of the Pre-marital test and henceforth encourage its practice, though some people are against the idea.

- iv. People of Nasarawa State also firmly believed that doing pre-marital screening will strengthen the marital life of Muslim couples. This is based on the fact that it will allow the couple to know their health status and that will give them confidence in their partner.*
- v. The study also found that some Muslims in Nasarawa State are too negligent about their current health status. Hence, they do not know their current health status neither do they know of their partner.*

CONCLUSION

The level of marriage conducted in Nasarawa State without pre-marital test is becoming alarming. Most couples in Nasarawa State felt disturbed on the issue of pre-marital tests for the fear of a result that could deteriorate their plan of marriage. This study assessed pre-marital tests among Muslim couples in Nasarawa State to ascertain the practice and attitudes of people towards the pre-marital test. An overview of the pre-marital test by a couple from an Islamic perspective. Thus, it, first of all, identify the concept of marriage in Islam, the possible reasons for the pre-marital test, the significance of the pre-marital test and the position of Islam on the pre-marital test.

People's awareness about pre-marital health tests of genetic disorders and deadly transmitted diseases influenced their choice of marriage partner among Muslims of Nasarawa State. The findings of this study found out that the level of awareness about the significance of pre-marital screening for couples is increasing with few numbers of people disdaining it because of the fear of an unfavourable result that might hinder the planning of their wedding. Encouraging Muslims to undergo pre-marital tests will enhance a better society with fewer diseases.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Pre-marital health screening for genetic disorders among undergraduate students should be intensified to prevent any inherited diseases from being passed to their offspring's.*
- ii. Intensive enlightenment campaign on pre-marital genotype testing before marriage should also be done by government and institutions through the media, alongside health education on genetic disease and its prevention right from primary school level.*
- iii. Muslim Scholars leaders should educate youths on the importance of pre-marital genotype screening and should be made a criterion before marriages are conducted.*

- iv. Government and Non-government organizations should provide free genotype testing and counselling centres in all areas of the country including the rural areas.
 - v. Government and Non-government organizations should ensure that facilities for pre-marital genotype screening are available and easily accessible nationwide.
 - vi. Adequate and immediate concern towards the threats of incompatibility that pre-marital health screening of genetic disorder would have should be intensified among Muslims of Nasarawa State to prevent the risk of producing sickle cell patients.
 - vii. Muslims should be sensitized and encouraged on pre-marital health screening of genetic disorders.
 - viii. Muslims should be encouraged to carry out pre-marital health screening to reduce the risk of spreading sexually transmitted infections such as syphilis.
- With hope for our society to be HIV/AIDS-free, STDs STIs etc I conclude this humble work.*

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QUESTIONNAIRE BIO-DATA

1. Sex: Male [] Female []
2. Age: 1-18 [] 19-30 [] 31 above []

3. Educational Background: FSLC [] SSCE [] ND/NCE [] B.Sc Degree [] Post Graduate []
4. Islamic Knowledge: Basic [] Advanced [] Very Advanced []

QUESTIONS

1. Do you know about Pre-marital test? (a) Yes [] (b) No []
2. Which of them you know (a) HIV/AIDS [] (b) STI/STDs [] Genotype [] Hepatitis [] All of the above []
3. Do you do it before marriage or intend to do it? (a) Yes [] (b) No []
4. Do you support the idea of pre-marital test? (a) Strongly Agree [] (b) Agree [] (c) Indifference [] (d) Disagree [] (e) Strongly Disagree []
5. From your understanding of Islam, what is the position of Sharia on the Pre-marital test?
(a) Unanimously (b) Recommended (c) Lawful (d) Hated (e) Unlawful
6. Do you think it should be encouraged? (a) Yes [] (b) No []
7. Are people of the Lafia metropolis firmly engaged in pre-marital screening? (a) Yes [] (b) No []
8. Do you think doing it will strengthen the Marital life of Muslim couples in Lafia? (a) Yes [] (b) No []
9. Do you know your status? (a) Yes [] (b) No []
10. Do you know the status of your partner? (a) yes [] (b) No []

